

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

**Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)
Protocol for Manure sampling**

[Compartment 2]

**Version 1
May/2020**

Table of Contents

	Page
1. Description	3
2. Equipment	3
3. Procedure	3
4. Sample identifiers	5
5. References	6

1. Description

The present protocol describes how to sample manure. There are three types of manure: solid, semi-solid and liquid manure. Manure with greater than 20% solids is classified as dry manure and is handled as a solid. Manure with 10% to 20% solids is classified as semi-solid manure and can usually be handled as a liquid. Manure with less than 10% solids is classified as liquid manure. Solid manure is generally stored on a concrete pad with runoff collection and may be uncovered or covered. Both semi-solid and liquid manure are handled with pumps, pipes, tank wagons, or irrigation equipment and they usually require the use of pumps to provide thorough agitation before sampling.

- Manure sampling in Austria and Portugal

Liquid (Austria) or semi-solid (Portugal) manure is collected from slurry pits either with a concrete cover or uncovered (open-air).

- Manure sampling in Czech Republic and Estonia

Liquid manure is collected by a sampling tap from a covered slurry pit (Czech Republic) or from a slurry tank (Estonia).

- Manure sampling in Great Britain

Solid manure is collected from open air piles

2. Equipment

- 10L plastic bucket
- Special sampling devices to sample manure in ponds or lagoons.
- Sampling scoop
- Rubber gloves
- Safety mask
- Disinfectant
- Sterile plastic containers or sterile bags

3. Procedure

3.1 Precautions

Gases such as hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and ammonia (NH₃) can cause symptoms ranging from headaches and eye irritation to death depending on length of exposure and gas concentration. Use always personal protective equipment when manipulating manure. Likewise process the samples in the laboratory, under the lamina flow with a mask.

3.2 Solid manure stored in open air manure heaps

- Put on rubber gloves, safety glasses and and mask
- Mix the manure to ensure homogeneity of the sample
- Collect up to 1.5 kg of manure in multiple sub-samples from various places and depths in the manure pile with a sample scoop, and place them in the clean plastic bucket.
- Mix the sample in the bucket manually.
- Distribute the manure in the different sampling containers (table 1a). **Do not to fill the sample containers completely up to the edge!** This allows for expansion due to the release of manure gases. **Do not use a glass container to store or transport manure samples!**
- Label the sample containers.
- Refrigerate and send immediately the samples to the laboratory to reduce the microbiological activity and the amount of gases released.
- Upon arrival, process immediately the subsample intended for microbiological analysis. If this is not possible, keep it refrigerated for a maximum of 24h with the cap of the container or bag slightly open until processing.
- For other non-microbiological analysis, immediately freeze the samples until processing.

Table 1a. Quantities to be distributed among the containers for solid manure.

Analysis	Task	Minimum quantity (g)	Container	Transport
Antibiotics (WP4)	4.2	50 g	PET sterile dark bottles	-20 °C
Elements (WP4)	4.7	250 g	PET sterile bottles/bags	-20 °C
Microbiology (WP2, WP3)	2.3, 2.4, 3.1	100 g	PET sterile bottles/bags	4 °C

3.3 Semi-solid and liquid manure stored in slurry pits or tanks (e.g: Austria, Czech Republic) or sludge lagoons (e.g: Portugal)

- Sterilize the sampling vessel (e.g. bucket)
- Put on rubber gloves, safety glasses and and mask
- Mix the manure to ensure homogeneity of the sample by pumping 10-15 times.
- For slurry ponds or tanks, fill the bucket with at least 1.5L of manure using liquid manure sampling device (e.g: telescopic fiberglass pole). For sludge lagoons, collect 10 subsamples every 30 cm in depth and various locations with a pipe and thoroughly mix the subsamples to make a composite sample of approximately 1.5L.
- Stir the manure in the bucket ensuring that any solids are suspended.
- Distribute the manure in the different sampling containers (table 1b). **Do not to fill the sample containers completely up to the edge!** This allows for expansion due to the release of manure gases. Do not use a glass container to store or transport manure samples!
- Label the sample containers.
- Refrigerate and send immediately the samples to the laboratory to reduce the microbiological activity and the amount of gases released
- Upon arrival, process immediately the subsample intended for microbiological analysis. If this is not possible, keep it refrigerated for a maximum of 24h with the cap of the container slightly open until processing.
- For other non-microbiological analysis, immediately freeze the samples until processing.

Table 1b. Volumes to be distributed among the containers for liquid or semi-solid manure.

Analysis	Task	Minimum volume (ml)	Container	Transport
Antibiotics (WP4)	4.2	150 ml	PET sterile dark bottles	-20 °C
Elements (WP4)	4.7	50 ml	PET sterile bottles	-20 °C
Microbiology (WP2, WP3)	2.3, 2.4, 3.1	500 ml	PET sterile bottles	4 °C

4. Sample identifiers for manure samples:

Sample Reference	Description	Type of sample	Scheduled Month
Austria			
AT20-M1	Austria, manure, spring	Liquid manure	Apr 20
AT20-M2	Austria, manure, summer	Liquid manure	Jul 20
AT20-M3	Austria, manure, autumn	Liquid manure	Oct 20
AT20-M4	Austria, manure, winter	Liquid manure	Jan 21
Czech Republic			
AT20-M1	Czech Republic, manure, spring	Liquid manure	Apr 20
AT20-M2	Czech Republic, manure, summer	Liquid manure	Aug 20
AT20-M3	Czech Republic, manure, autumn	Liquid manure	Oct 20
AT20-M4	Czech Republic, manure, winter	Liquid manure	Dec 20
Estonia			
AT20-M1	Estonia, manure, summer	Liquid manure	May 20
AT20-M2	Estonia, manure, autumn	Liquid manure	Jun 20
AT20-M3	Estonia, manure, winter	Liquid manure	Oct 20
AT20-M4	Estonia, manure, spring	Liquid manure	Jan 21
Great Britain			
GB20-M1	Great Britain, manure, summer	Solid manure	Jul 20
GB20-M2	Great Britain, manure, autumn	Solid manure	Oct 20
GB20-M3	Great Britain, manure, winter	Solid manure	Jan 21
GB20-M4	Great Britain, manure, spring	Solid manure	Apr 21
Portugal			
PT20-M1	Portugal, manure, spring	Semi-solid manure	Jul 20
PT20-M2	Portugal, manure, summer	Semi-solid manure	Oct 20
PT20-M3	Portugal, manure, autumn	Semi-solid manure	Jan 21
PT20-M4	Portugal, manure, winter	Semi-solid manure	Apr 21

5. References

- Department of Soil Health and Plant Nutrition, AGES, Vienna, Austria.
- Miller CMF, Heguy JM, Karle BM, Price PL, Meyer D. Optimizing accuracy of sampling protocols to measure nutrient content of solid manure. *Waste Manag.* 2019;85:121–130. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2018.12.021
- Ron E. Sheffield and Richard J. Norel. *Manure and Wastewater Sampling.* University of Idaho, 2007.
- Van den Meersche T, Rasschaert G, Haesebrouck F, et al. Presence and fate of antibiotic residues, antibiotic resistance genes and zoonotic bacteria during biological swine manure treatment. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf.* 2019;175:29-38. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.01.127